

Complexes of palladium using di-2-pyridyl ketone as ligand : Synthesis, structure and, spectral and catalytic properties[†]

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Abstract : During the reaction of di-2-pyridyl ketone (dpk) with Na₂[PdCl₄] in alcoholic media, the C=O fragment of dpk undergoes facile solvolysis and the transformed di-2-pyridyl ketone (dpk^{ROH}, R = Me or H) binds to palladium as NN-donor. When the reaction is carried out in refluxing methanol, a mono-complex of type [Pd(dpk^{MeOH})Cl₂] is obtained. A similar reaction in ethanol affords a bis-complex of type [Pd(dpk^{HOH})₂]Cl₂. Structure of both the complexes have been determined by X-ray crystallography. In acetonitrile solution the [Pd(dpk^{MeOH})Cl₂] and [Pd(dpk^{HOH})₂]Cl₂ complexes show intense absorptions in the visible and ultraviolet region, origin of which has been probed through DFT calculations. These two palladium complexes are found to be efficient catalysts for Suzuki cross-coupling reactions.

Keywords : Palladium complexes, di-2-pyridyl ketone, spectral study, DFT calculation, Suzuki coupling.

Introduction

Coordination chemistry of palladium has been attracting considerable current attention¹, particularly because of the growing interest in the use of palladium complexes as catalysts in C-C cross-coupling reactions of different types (such as Suzuki, Heck, Sonogashira, etc.)². There are several advantages of using palladium complexes as catalysts over other species, and it is due to this unique nature of palladium that we are witnessing the remarkable success in catalytic C-C cross-coupling reactions³. Though palladium complexes with phosphine type ligands (such as [Pd(PPh₃)₄]) are always a favorite choice as precatalysts for such reactions⁴, complexes with ligands of other types are also gaining popularity with time⁵. In this context, complexation of palladium by judiciously chosen ligands is of significant importance. In the present piece of work, which has originated from our interest in the chemistry of palladium complexes in general⁶, and our recent experience in utilizing such complexes in catalytic C-C cross-coupling reactions in particular^{6a}, we have selected di-2-pyridyl ketone (abbreviated as dpk) as the

principal ligand and Na₂[PdCl₄] as the source of palladium. It needs to be mentioned here that though binding of the dpk ligand to a metal center as bidentate NN-donor forming a stable six-membered chelate ring (A) is reported in the literature⁷, the C=O fragment of this ligand often undergoes facile solvolysis during complexation,

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and the hydroxyl group, thus generated, is known to play a vital role in the binding modes displayed by the transformed ligand. If the hydroxyl group does not participate in coordination, binding to a single metal center in the NN-mode (**B**) takes place⁸. When the hydroxyl group participates in coordination, it undergoes deprotonation and binding to two metal centers (**C**) or three metal centers (**D**) is observed⁹. The primary objective of the present study has been to synthesize mono- and bis-complexes of palladium using the dpk ligand and explore their spectral and catalytic properties. Reactions of the dpk ligand with $\text{Na}_2[\text{PdCl}_4]$ have indeed afforded interesting mono- and bis-complexes of palladium, and herein we describe the chemistry of these complexes, with special reference to their formation, structure and, spectral and catalytic properties.

Experimental

Materials :

Commercial PdCl_2 , purchased from Arora Matthey (Kolkata), was converted to $\text{Na}_2[\text{PdCl}_4]$ by following a reported procedure¹⁰. Di-2-pyridyl ketone was procured from Aldrich. All other chemicals and solvents were reagent grade commercial materials and were used as received.

Preparation of the complexes :

$[\text{Pd}(\text{dpk}^{\text{MeOH}})\text{Cl}_2]$: To a solution of di-2-pyridyl ketone (60 mg, 0.34 mmol) in hot methanol (30 mL) was added $\text{Na}_2[\text{PdCl}_4]$ (100 mg, 0.34 mmol) dissolved in 10 mL of methanol. The resulting solution was heated at reflux for 2 h. The solution was cooled to room temperature, and $[\text{Pd}(\text{dpk}^{\text{MeOH}})\text{Cl}_2]$, precipitated as a reddish-pink crystalline solid, was collected by filtration, washed with cold methanol and dried in air. Yield : 92%. Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2\text{Cl}_2\text{Pd}$: C, 36.64; H, 3.05; N, 7.12; Found : C, 36.33; H, 2.91; N, 7.03%. $^1\text{H NMR}^{11}$: 3.16 (d, 3H, J 4.5), 7.59 (t, H, J 5.4), 7.98 (d, 2H, J 4.2), 8.15 (t, H, J 7.8), 8.76 (s, 1H), 8.92 (d, 1H, J 4.2) 9.07 (s, 1H).

$[\text{Pd}(\text{dpk}^{\text{HOH}})_2]\text{Cl}_2$: To a solution of di-2-pyridyl ketone (124 mg, 0.70 mmol) in hot ethanol (30 mL), was added $\text{Na}_2[\text{PdCl}_4]$ (100 mg, 0.34 mmol) dissolved in 10 mL of ethanol. The resulting solution was heated at reflux for 4 h, whereby $[\text{Pd}(\text{dpk}^{\text{HOH}})_2]\text{Cl}_2$ started to precipitate as a reddish-brown crystalline solid, which was

collected by filtration, washed with cold ethanol and dried in air. Yield : 91%. Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_4\text{N}_4\text{Pd}$: C, 51.76; H, 3.92; N, 10.98; Found : C, 51.27; H, 3.89; N, 10.87%. $^1\text{H NMR}$: 7.49 (t, 4H, J 6.3), 7.94 (d, 4H, J 7.8), 8.07 (t, 4H, J 7.5), 8.42 (s, 2H), 8.79 (s, 2H), 8.87 (d, 4H, J 5.4).

Physical measurements :

Microanalyses (C, H and N) were performed using a Heraeus Carlo Erba 1108 elemental analyzer. $^1\text{H NMR}$ spectra were recorded in d^6 -DMSO solution on a Bruker Avance DPX 300 NMR spectrometer using TMS as the internal standard. IR spectra were obtained on a Shimadzu FTIR-8300 spectrometer with samples prepared as KBr pellets. Electronic spectra were recorded on a JASCO V-570 spectrophotometer. Ground-state structures and energy calculations for both the complexes were carried out by density functional theory (DFT) method, based on the crystallographic coordinates, using the Gaussian 03 package¹² using B3LYP/[SDD/6-31g(d,p)] basis set.

Crystallography :

Single crystals of $[\text{Pd}(\text{dpk}^{\text{MeOH}})\text{Cl}_2]$ and $[\text{Pd}(\text{dpk}^{\text{HOH}})_2]\text{Cl}_2$ were obtained by slow evaporation of solvent from solutions of the complexes in ethanol. Selected crystal data and data collection parameters are given in Table 1. Data were collected on a Bruker SMART Apex CCD area detector using graphite monochromated $\text{Mo-K}\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 0.71073 \text{ \AA}$). X-ray data reduction, structure solution and refinement were done using SHELXS-97 and SHELXL-97 programs¹³. The structures were solved by the direct methods. CCDC 828711 and 828712 contain the supplementary crystallographic data.

Catalysis – General procedure for the Suzuki coupling reactions :

In a typical run, an oven-dried 10 mL round bottom flask was charged with a known mole percent of catalyst. Cs_2CO_3 (1.7 mmol), phenylboronic acid (1.2 mmol) and aryl bromide (1 mmol) with ethanol-toluene 1 : 1 mixture (4 mL). The flask was placed in a preheated oil bath at required temp. After the specified time the flask was removed from the oil bath and water (20 mL) was added, followed by extraction with ether ($4 \times 10 \text{ mL}$). The combined organic layers were washed with water ($3 \times 10 \text{ mL}$), dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 , and filtered. Solvent was removed under vacuum. The residue was dissolved

Table 1. Crystallographic data for [Pd(dpk^{MeOH})Cl₂] and [Pd(dpk^{HOH})₂]Cl₂

	[Pd(dpk ^{MeOH})Cl ₂]	[Pd(dpk ^{HOH}) ₂]Cl ₂
Empirical formula	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂ Cl ₂ Pd	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₄ Pd. 2(Cl). H ₂ O
Fw	393.56	599.59
Space group	Monoclinic, P2 ₁ /n	Monoclinic, C2/c
a (Å)	9.106(3)	14.860(2)
b (Å)	11.784(5)	12.365(2)
c (Å)	12.625(4)	14.360(2)
γ (°)	91.509(15)	91.146(3)
V (Å ³)	1354.3(8)	2638.0(7)
Z	4	4
Cryst. size (mm ³)	0.04 × 0.35 × 0.37	0.22 × 0.24 × 0.25
T (K)	296	296
μ (mm ⁻¹)	1.762	1.046
R1 ^a	0.0311	0.0577
wR2 ^b	0.0716	0.2044
GOF ^c	1.04	1.12

$$^a R1 = \frac{\sum ||F_o| - |F_c||}{\sum |F_o|}$$

$$^b wR2 = \frac{[\sum \{w(F_o^2 - F_c^2)^2\} / \sum \{w(F_o^2)\}]^{1/2}}$$

$$^c GOF = [\sum \{w(F_o^2 - F_c^2)^2\} / (M - N)]^{1/2}, \text{ where } M \text{ is the number of reflections and } N \text{ is the number of parameters refined.}$$

in CDCl₃ and analyzed by ¹H NMR. Percent conversions were determined against the remaining aryl bromide¹⁴.

Results and discussion

Synthesis and structure :

As delineated in the introduction, both mono- and bis-complexes of palladium, using di-2-pyridyl ketone (dpk) as the ligand, have been prepared with an aim to study the efficiency of these complexes towards C–C cross-coupling reactions. Reaction of the dpk ligand with Na₂[PdCl₄] in 1 : 1 mole ratio in methanolic medium affords the mono-complex in excellent yield. Preliminary characterization (microanalytical and spectral) data on this complex are found to be in fairly good agreement with its composition. In order to authenticate the composition of this complex, as well as to find out the binding mode of the dpk ligand in it, structure of this mono-complex has been determined by X-ray crystallography. The structure is shown in Fig. 1 and selected bond parameters are given in Table 2. The structure reveals that during the course of the synthetic reaction the dpk ligand has undergone a chemical transformation, whereby the C=O fragment of dpk has been converted into a C(OCH₃)OH fragment via reaction with the solvent (MeOH). The transformed dpk

Fig. 1. View of the [Pd(dpk^{MeOH})Cl₂] complex

ligand, referred to as dpk^{MeOH} from now on, is coordinated to palladium in the N,N-mode (B, R = Me). Two chloride ions are also coordinated to the metal center, which are fulfilling both the charge and coordination number of the metal center. This mono-complex is therefore denoted as [Pd(dpk^{MeOH})Cl₂]. In this complex palladium

Table 2 Selected bond distances and bond angles for [Pd(dpk^{MeOH})₂]Cl₂ and [Pd(dpk^{HOH})₂]Cl₂

[Pd(dpk ^{MeOH}) ₂]Cl ₂			
Bond distances (Å)			
Pd(1) N(1)	2.028(3)	C(1) C(3)	1.526(5)
Pd(1) N(2)	2.044(3)	C(1) C(8)	1.523(5)
Pd(1) Cl(1)	2.2953(14)	C(1) O(2)	1.371(5)
Pd(1) Cl(2)	2.2891(14)	C(1) O(1)	1.430(5)
		O(1) C(2)	1.461(5)
Bond angles (°)			
N(1) Pd(1) N(2)	86.46(11)	N(1) Pd(1) Cl(2)	177.75(8)
		N(2) Pd(1) Cl(1)	176.92(8)
[Pd(dpk ^{HOH}) ₂]Cl ₂			
Bond distances (Å)			
Pd(1) N(1)	2.018(6)	C(6) C(1)	1.538(7)
Pd(1) N(2)	2.021(4)	C(6) C(7)	1.529(6)
		C(6) O(1)	1.372(6)
		C(6) O(2)	1.393(6)
Bond angles (°)			
N(1) Pd(1) N(2)	93.07(17)	N(1) Pd(1) N(2a)	86.93(17)

Fig 2. View of the [Pd(dpk^{HOH})₂]²⁺ complex

is nested in an N₂Cl₂ coordination sphere, which is slightly distorted from ideal square planar geometry, as reflected in the bond parameters around palladium. It is relevant to mention here that synthesis of this complex via an entirely different route and determination of its crystal structure was reported earlier^{8a}

Reaction of the di-2-pyridyl ketone (dpk) ligand with Na₂[PdCl₄] in 2 : 1 mole ratio, carried out in refluxing ethanol, affords the bis-complex in very good yield. While the preliminary characterization data on this complex were in favor of the bis-composition, crystal structure of this complex has also been solved for an unambiguous identification of this complex with regard to binding mode of the dpk ligand. The structure (shown in Fig 2) shows that the dpk ligand has again undergone a chemical transformation during the complex formation, which is slightly different than that observed in the previous complex. Here the C=O fragment of dpk has reacted with water, present in commercial ethanol, and thus gets converted into a C(OH)OH fragment. Two such transformed dpk ligands, referred to as dpk^{HOH} from now on, are coordinated to palladium in the N,N-mode (B, R = H). The N₄ coordination sphere, thus created around palladium, is nearly square planar. The bond parameters in this bis-complex

(Table 2) are found to be comparable to those in the mono-complex. In the crystal lattice two chloride ions are present for each complex cation to balance the dipositive charge of it. This bis-complex is therefore represented as [Pd(dpk^{HOH})₂]Cl₂. It is to be noted here that the crystal structure of this particular complex was published before^{8c}

Spectral properties

Both the [Pd(dpk^{MeOH})₂]Cl₂ and [Pd(dpk^{HOH})₂]Cl₂ complexes are found to be diamagnetic, which corresponds to the divalent state of palladium (d⁸ S = 0) in them. ¹H NMR spectra of these complexes have been recorded in d⁶-DMSO solution. Each complex shows characteristic signals arising from the pyridyl fragments of the modified-dpk ligand. In addition, in [Pd(dpk^{MeOH})₂]Cl₂ characteristic signals for the OMe and hydroxyl groups are also distinctly observed. Similarly, in [Pd(dpk^{HOH})₂]Cl₂ signals for the hydroxyl groups could be clearly identified. Infrared spectra of both the complexes show many bands of varying intensities within 4000–400 cm⁻¹. Assignment of each individual band to a specific vibration has not been attempted. However, several sharp bands (e.g. near 3445, 2360, 1626, 1538, 1466, 1382, 1156, 1096 and 753 cm⁻¹) are observed in both the complexes which are attributable to presence of the modified dpk ligand(s) in these complexes. The strong C=O stretching band at 1750 cm⁻¹ in the uncoordinated dpk ligand is

found to be absent in the IR spectra of the complexes, which corresponds to the chemical modification of this fragment during complexation. A broad peak near 3444 cm^{-1} , observed in both the complexes, indicates the presence of hydroxyl group(s). Hence the ^1H NMR and IR spectral data of the $[\text{Pd}(\text{dpk}^{\text{MeOH}})\text{Cl}_2]$ and $[\text{Pd}(\text{dpk}^{\text{HOH}})_2]\text{Cl}_2$ complexes are in well agreement with their crystal structures.

The $[\text{Pd}(\text{dpk}^{\text{MeOH}})\text{Cl}_2]$ and $[\text{Pd}(\text{dpk}^{\text{HOH}})_2]\text{Cl}_2$ complexes are found to be insoluble in chloroform and dichloromethane, poorly soluble in methanol, ethanol and acetone, but soluble in acetonitrile, dimethylformamide and dimethylsulphoxide producing reddish-pink and brown solutions, respectively. Electronic spectra of the complexes have been recorded in acetonitrile solutions. Spectral data are presented in Table 3. The $[\text{Pd}(\text{dpk}^{\text{MeOH}})\text{Cl}_2]$

Table 3. Electronic spectral data^a

Compound	λ_{max} , nm (ϵ , $\text{M}^{-1}\text{ cm}^{-1}$)
$[\text{Pd}(\text{dpk}^{\text{MeOH}})\text{Cl}_2]$	544 (882), 272 ^s (5723), 208 (28176)
$[\text{Pd}(\text{dpk}^{\text{HOH}})_2]\text{Cl}_2$	274 ^s (9968), 214 (31486)

^aIn acetonitrile ^sShoulder

complex shows a weak absorption in the visible region, and two intense absorptions in the ultraviolet region. However, the $[\text{Pd}(\text{dpk}^{\text{HOH}})_2]\text{Cl}_2$ complex shows only two intense absorptions in the ultraviolet region. Though the lowest energy absorption in this bis-complex has its λ_{max} in the ultraviolet region (274 nm), a significant part of the absorption profile lies in the visible region, which appears to be responsible for imparting the brown color. To understand more about the origin of the visible colors of these two complexes, DFT calculations have been performed on both of them. Electron distribution in the highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO) and lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (LUMO) for the $[\text{Pd}(\text{dpk}^{\text{MeOH}})\text{Cl}_2]$ complex is shown in Fig. 3, and composition of these molecular orbitals is given in Table 4. The HOMO has major (~60%) contribution from the two coordinated chlorides and relatively less (~39%) contribution from palladium. The LUMO is delocalized primarily (~90%)

Fig. 3 Frontier orbital diagram of $[\text{Pd}(\text{dpk}^{\text{MeOH}})\text{Cl}_2]$

over the dpk^{MeOH} ligand. Hence the lowest-energy absorption, observed at 544 nm, is assignable to a charge-transfer transition from a filled orbital having mixed (metal + chloride) character to a vacant π^* -orbital of the dpk^{MeOH} ligand. In the $[\text{Pd}(\text{dpk}^{\text{HOH}})_2]\text{Cl}_2$ complex, both the HOMO and LUMO are delocalized mostly (> 93%) over the two dpk^{HOH} ligands (Fig. 4, Table 4). Hence the lowest energy absorption observed at 274 nm is assignable to a charge-transfer transition within orbitals of the dpk^{HOH} ligands.

Fig. 4. Frontier orbital diagram of $[\text{Pd}(\text{dpk}^{\text{HOH}})_2]\text{Cl}_2$.

Table 4. Composition of selected molecular orbitals

Complex	Contributing fragments	% Contribution of fragments to	
		HOMO	LUMO
$[\text{Pd}(\text{dpk}^{\text{MeOH}})\text{Cl}_2]$	Pd	38.51	8.56
	Cl	59.73	1.87
	dpk^{MeOH}	1.76	89.57
$[\text{Pd}(\text{dpk}^{\text{HOH}})_2]\text{Cl}_2$	Pd	1.13	6.17
	dpk^{HOH}	98.87	93.83

Catalysis :

The fact, that palladium complexes are well known to serve as efficient catalysts in bringing about C-C cross coupling reactions of different types³, has prompted us to explore such catalytic properties in the $[\text{Pd}(\text{dpk}^{\text{MeOH}})\text{Cl}_2]$ and $[\text{Pd}(\text{dpk}^{\text{HOH}})_2]\text{Cl}_2$ complexes. The catalytic activity both these complexes have been examined for Suzuki type coupling of phenylboronic acid and aryl bromides to yield the biphenyl product. Three different aryl bromides, viz. *p*-bromoacetophenone, *p*-bromobenzaldehyde and *p*-bromobenzonitrile, have been used for the Suzuki reaction with phenylboronic acid. While both the complexes were found to display notable catalytic activity, the efficiency of $[\text{Pd}(\text{dpk}^{\text{MeOH}})\text{Cl}_2]$ has been found to be higher than that of $[\text{Pd}(\text{dpk}^{\text{HOH}})_2]\text{Cl}_2$ (Table 5). For example, using $[\text{Pd}(\text{dpk}^{\text{MeOH}})\text{Cl}_2]$ as catalyst the targeted Suzuki coupling reactions were achieved, under relatively mild experimental condition, in high yield as well as reasonably high turnover number (entries 1-3). The same coupling reactions, when carried out using $[\text{Pd}(\text{dpk}^{\text{HOH}})_2]\text{Cl}_2$ as the catalyst, needed longer times (entries 4-6) for giving similar yields of the products. Better catalytic efficiency of the mono complex over the bis-complex is attributed to the presence of easily dissociable Pd-Cl bonds in the mono complex.

Conclusion :

The present study shows that di-2-pyridyl ketone (dpk) undergoes facile solvolysis during its reaction with $\text{Na}_2[\text{PdCl}_4]$ and, depending on the experimental condition, affords mono- or bis-complex, where the transformed di-2-pyridyl ketone (dpk^{ROH} , R = Me or H) binds to palladium as NN-donor. The present study also demonstrates that both the mono- and bis-complex can efficiently catalyze Suzuki type C-C cross-coupling reactions.

Table 5. Suzuki cross-coupling of aryl bromides with phenyl-boronic acid^a

Entry	R	Pd-Catalyst	Time (h)	Cat. amt. (mol %)	Conversn (%) ^b	TON ^c
1	COMe	[Pd(dpk ^{MeOH})Cl ₂]	5	0.5	> 99	200
2	CHO	[Pd(dpk ^{MeOH})Cl ₂]	7	0.5	> 99	200
3	CN	[Pd(dpk ^{MeOH})Cl ₂]	8	0.5	> 99	200
4	COMe	[Pd(dpk ^{HOH}) ₂]Cl ₂	6	0.5	> 99	200
5	CHO	[Pd(dpk ^{HOH}) ₂]Cl ₂	9	0.5	> 99	200
6	CN	[Pd(dpk ^{HOH}) ₂]Cl ₂	10	0.5	> 99	200

^aReaction conditions : aryl bromide (1.0 mmol), phenylboronic acid (1.2 mmol), Cs₂CO₃ (1.7 mmol), Pd-catalyst, solvent (4 mL).

^bDetermined by ¹H NMR on the basis of residual aryl bromide¹⁴.

^cTON = turnover number ((mol of product)/(mol of catalyst)).

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